

Constitution

Beginning

This constitution was written to keep the peace in every community; it is superior only as long as it does not contradict.

Title I. General Principles and Terms

Part I. General Principles

Article 1.

Management Type

Being is the state; It is a state with its nation, people and army, with its principles and restrictions. The state is a nation-state with its own language and is principled with the principles of statism, nationalism and populism; It is a constitutional and democratic kingdom that is restrained and inconsistent in its principles.

The king is the king of the basic race; He is the head of the people and the army.

The state does not recognize expansion or exploitation with the military; It is a state with its own resources and fields.

Its motto is "Peace at home, peace in the world".

Article 2.

Legal Identity

The internal and external legal identity determined by the state is shaped according to the understanding of individual freedom and social rule of law.

The same understandings are also essential in practice, in accordance with the conceptual spirit of the Constitution with universal values.

Article 3.

Separation of Powers

The separation of legislative, executive and judicial powers and the principle of separation of powers are essential. The separation of powers is not an

absolute superiority or independence between powers; It is a civilized division of labor and cooperation.

State organs are autonomous.

The laws are used by state bodies as organic laws, accepting the constitution as binding. The form of autonomous functioning, the rights and responsibilities of responsible people are determined separately by organic laws.

Laws contrary to the conceptual spirit of the Constitution cannot be derived.

Article 4.

Leadership Understanding

Under the leadership of wisdom and sages, classification is essential; For this, special and general titles, which can be personal and corporate, are used.

The administrator is the supervisor and he is innocent.

Article 5.

Citizen

The citizen is the one who feels himself to belong to his community; the state owns it. Citizenship is a principled responsibility; its duty is the present and future of the society together with its past achievements. The principles of application are the same as in the conscience of the society.

Citizens wish each other well when they meet.

Article 6.

Social Order

It is a male-dominated society; In this society, the man is the leader of the woman.

A contemporary order aims; For this purpose, it is essential to live with the principles of self-sacrifice and volunteerism.

The first duty of every citizen of the country, without exception, is to protect the current order unconditionally, regardless of the situation he is in.

Sovereignty belongs to the nation unconditionally, without any political or ideological purpose.

Part II.

General provisions

Section I.

Principles of Existence

Article 7.

Statehood

The state is united in the same ideal with its nation and people on a legal basis; let the people live so that the state can live.

State; It is an indivisible whole with its nation and people, its army and laws.

May our state exist.

Article 8.

Nationalism

The Nation-State does not distinguish a non-racial citizen from a racial citizen; recognizes him with the same sacred values.

Society remembers the past, lives in the present and marches into the future, under the leadership of the basic race and in their name; Success or failure in the same holy ideal that holds society together without ethnic identity is, with this understanding, the success or failure of the basic race.

Nationalism cannot become a political ideal.

Thank you, our nation.

Article 9.

Populism

Equality between persons is essential; No privilege is given to any person or group in the society because of their identity.

The main thing is to become a citizen by working for the benefit of the individual.

May our people grow.

Section II. Order of the State

Article I. Political Order

Article 10.

Provinces

According to the principles of this constitution, the state order is the basic campus order. State; It is governed by four main states, east, west, north and south. States are made up of provinces. It consists of provinces, districts and sub-districts.

The states are not bound by a contractual commitment, but are a procedural element of unconditional loyalty.

Article 11.

Capital

The State acquires a Capital, which is the seat of the executive and represents it internationally.

In an extraordinary situation, a city cannot be made a capital city for reasons that will damage the defense and administrative functioning.

Article 12.

Administration

The political administration under the executive is carried out only with a centralized administration and with the National Assembly in the provinces.

In exceptional cases other than the essential, guardianship authority and public legal personality are regulated by organic law.

The smallest administrative element is the headman's office. The headman is only responsible for the parish.

Article 13.

Property

Everyone has the freedom to work and contract in the field they want. Special It is free to establish enterprises.

The state ensures that private enterprises operate in accordance with the requirements of the national economy and social purposes, takes measures to ensure that it works in safety and stability.

**Article II.
Management Order**

I. Legislative and Executive Order

Article 14.

Assembly Layout

Parliamentary order is essential in representation.

The Legislative and Executive Council is the Grand National Assembly. The Judicial Council is the Constitutional Court. Army Council is the Gökkuş Council. Mutual judicial review is essential with the principle of separation of powers and legal disputes; The legal supremacy in the judiciary rests with the judge.

There is the National Assembly in the province and the State Assembly in the state; They do not have the authority to use the army.

In the voting system, the majority of votes and the quorum for the number of members are essential for acceptance.

Article 15.

Order of Government

The order of government is essential in the implementation of democracy.

The government is elected by the people according to the constitutional principles and takes office; responsible for the legislative and executive.

Ministries; It is divided into Ministries of Internal and Foreign Affairs, Defense, Education, Economy, Health and Justice and the Prime Ministry. The government takes charge in these ministries and is responsible for managing and developing the undersecretariats or opening new undersecretariats.

For the resignation of the government, a no-confidence question in the Grand National Assembly is essential.

The government has the authority to use the army according to the principles of organic law.

II. Judicial Order

Article 16.

Criminal Sanction

The exercise of judicial power rests with the courts in the name of the people.

The legislative and executive organs and the administration must comply with court decisions; these organs and the administration cannot change the court decisions in any way and cannot enforce them, cannot delay.

III. Administrative Order

Article 17.

Government office

The state provides public services through public offices that are open to civil or official inspections and that have been previously introduced to the public.

The state shall fulfill its duties determined by the Constitution in social and economic fields, takes into account the priorities appropriate to its objectives and fulfills it to the extent of the adequacy of its financial resources.

Judicial remedy is open against all kinds of actions and actions of the administration.

Article 18.

Civil Service

General administration of the state, state economic enterprises and other public legal entities The essential and permanent duties required by the public services that they are obliged to carry out according to the principles of the law are carried out by civil servants and other public officials.

Qualifications, appointments, duties and powers, rights and obligations, salaries and allowances and other personnel matters of civil servants and other public officials are regulated by law.

Title II.

Laws

Part I.

Citizenship Laws

Section I.

Human rights

Article I.

the Fundamentals

Article 19.

Right

The universal and conceptual value of man is essential in determining the fundamental rights of the citizen; therefore the fundamental rights of the individual; They are natural rights that all people can enjoy, regardless of race, nationality, ethnic origin, religion, language and gender.

They are inviolable, inalienable and inalienable rights.

The state is obliged to develop and guarantee human rights through the laws it regulates. The state protects these rights against both legal authorities and the individual. In practice, the conceptual spirit of the constitution is essential.

Article 20.

Freedom

Human rights give every individual the freedom to remove unlawful barriers, make independent choices and develop their existence.

Although freedoms are unrestricted, they cannot be accepted except for social duties and responsibilities; Individuals have the right to live in peace and create opportunities for themselves.

Article 21.

Constraint

Rights and freedoms and their enjoyment are regulated by organic law and are all restricted.

Article II.

Provisions

I. Private life

Article 22.

Privacy

Private life; It is a private life that belongs to the individual, where the person chooses to exist independently of the environment, where the environment cannot have personal information and cannot influence his actions in this area. Private life also encompasses the inviolability of one's home and freedom of communication.

The person has the right to demand that his private life be respected.

Article 23.

Freedom of Communication

Everyone has the freedom of communication. Confidentiality of communication is essential. Unless there is a judge's decision duly given; In cases where delay is inconvenient, the authority authorized by law unless there is a written order; communication cannot be blocked and its privacy cannot be touched.

The public institutions and organizations to which the exceptions will be applied are specified in the law.

Article 24.

Housing Immunity

No one's home can be touched. Unless there is a judge's decision duly given; In cases where delay is inconvenient, the authority authorized by law unless there is a written order; no one's residence can be entered, searched, and the goods therein confiscated. The procedures and principles are as in the organic law.

II. Personal Immunity

Article 25.

Body Immunity

The state, together with all the elements that make up it, is the chief assurance of the development and maintenance of the material and spiritual existence of the person.

The person is incompatible with torture or human dignity; suppressing or hurting their material and spiritual existence; shall not be subjected to any treatment that may be regarded as detention. No one may be killed intentionally, except in the execution of a sentence given by the courts or in self-defense.

Except for medical obligations and the cases written in the law, the body integrity of the person cannot be touched; cannot be subjected to scientific and medical experiments without his consent.

Article 26.

Personal Freedom

Everyone has personal liberty and security. No one can be deprived of his liberty except through legal proceedings restricting his liberty.

Persons subjected to a process other than these principles, the damage they have suffered is paid by the state in accordance with the general principles of compensation law.

III. Environmental Right

Article 27.

Property Rights

It is the right that gives the right holder the right to use, enjoy and dispose of the goods. Everyone has the right to property.

This right can only be limited by law for the public interest. The use of the right to property can not be contrary to public interest.

Ownership is officially documented.

Article 28.

Freedom of residence and travel

Travel and relocation is a constitutionally protected right. Persons are free to leave the country. No one shall be arbitrarily deprived of the right to enter his own country.

The state respects the laws of that society for its people living in foreign societies; foreign visitors or permanent foreigners are responsible for the constitution.

The state recognizes international asylum claims and makes extradition when it deems necessary. The state recognizes the international security units and works together to ensure world peace.

IV. Operating Rights

Article 29.

Drudgery prohibition

Drudgery is prohibited.

Employment of persons in a job incompatible with their power, age and gender; It is drudgery for the administration to assign people by detention or to use them without consent in works that do not comply with the job description.

According to the form and principles in organic laws, compulsory national services in some cases are not considered forced labor.

Article 30.

Freedom of science and art

Everyone has the right to freely learn and teach, explain, disseminate and reserves the right to research in all fields. The state protects art and science activities, scientists and artists. Artwork and artist takes the necessary measures to protect, evaluate, support, and spread the love of art and science.

The entry and distribution of foreign publications in the country is free according to the principles of organic law.

V. Freedom of Faith and Thought

Article 31.

Freedom of Thought and Expression

Everyone has the right to express and disseminate their thoughts and opinions individually or collectively through words, writings, pictures or other means.

This freedom includes the freedom to receive or impart information or ideas without the intervention of official authorities.

No one to express their thoughts cannot be forced; cannot be blamed or blamed for his thoughts and opinions.

Article 32.

Freedom to express and disseminate thought

Everyone can express their thoughts and opinions individually, through words, writing, pictures or other means. or collectively, has the right to disclose and disseminate.

This freedom, without the intervention of official authorities it also includes the freedom to receive or impart information or ideas without notice. The provision of this paragraph is not against preventing broadcasts made by television, radio, cinema and similar means from being connected to the permission system.

The use of these freedoms may be restricted by the principles and procedures in the organic law.

Article 33.

Freedom of Religion and Conscience

Every person has the right to freedom of thought, conscience and religion; This right includes the freedom to change religion or opinion, and the freedom to manifest one's religion or opinion, individually or collectively, openly or privately, through teaching, practice, worship and rites.

No one can be compelled to participate in worship, religious rites and ceremonies, or to reveal their religious beliefs and convictions; cannot be condemned or blamed for their religious beliefs and convictions.

**Section II.
Social Rights**

**Article I.
Social Provisions**

I. Communities

Article 34.

Selection and Selection

Citizens are entitled to elect, be elected and engage in political activity independently or within a political party, in accordance with the conditions laid down in the law; has the right to form, join and leave parties, and participate in the referendum.

Selection and selection ages and constraints are as in organic laws.

Article 35.

Foundations and Societies

Everyone is free to form associations, join or unsubscribe from associations without prior permission.

No one can be compelled to become a member of an association or to remain a member of the association.

Freedom of association is limited to national security, public order, prevention of crime, general may be limited by law and for reasons of health and public morals and the protection of the freedoms of others.

The form, conditions and procedures to be applied in the exercise of the freedom of association are specified in the law.

Article 36.

Rally and Demonstrations

Everyone can organize unarmed and non-attacked meetings and demonstration marches without prior permission.

The right to assembly and demonstration only applies to the protection of national security, public order and the commission of a crime. prevention, protection of public health and morals or the rights and freedoms of others. for purposes and may be limited by law.

The form, conditions and conditions to be applied in the exercise of the right to organize meetings and demonstrations. procedures are indicated in the law.

Article 37.

Freedom of the Press

The press is free and cannot be censored. Establishing a printing house cannot be made conditional on obtaining permission and depositing financial guarantees.

The state shall take measures to ensure freedom of press and information. This includes its own measures.

Right of rectification and reply, but without prejudice to the dignity and honor of persons or in case of false publications about them, they are recognized and regulated by law.

The printing house and its annexes and press tools established as a press business in accordance with the law cannot be seized, confiscated or prevented from being operated on the grounds that they are tools of crime.

II. Petition and Use of Right

Article 38.

Petition

Citizens and residents residing within the borders of the country, on the basis of reciprocity foreigners about their wishes and complaints about themselves or the public, to the competent authorities and He has the right to apply in writing to the Chief Ombudsman on behalf of the Grand National Assembly.

The results of the applications concerning them shall be sent to the petitioners in writing without delay.

Article 39.

Exercise of Right

Anyone whose rights and freedoms recognized by the Constitution are violated, reserves the right to request the opportunity to apply without delay.

The state, in its transactions, determines which legal remedies and must state that he will apply to the authorities and the deadlines.

The damage suffered by the person as a result of unfair actions by official officials is also subject to the law. is compensated by the State. The right of recourse to the responsible official of the state is reserved.

Saying that the right will be used is not a threat crime.

Article II.
Social and Economic
Assurances

Article 40.

Social Security

Everyone has the right to social security. The state takes the necessary measures to ensure this security and establishes the organization.

The state protects the widows and orphans of the martyrs of war and duty, the disabled and veterans, and provide a decent standard of living in society.

The state takes measures to ensure the protection of the disabled and their adaptation to social life. The elderly are protected by the State, State aid to the elderly and other rights and facilities to be provided regulated by law.

The state takes all kinds of measures to reintegrate children in need of protection into society.

Article 41.

Health, environment and housing

Everyone has the right to live in a healthy and balanced environment.

To improve the environment, to protect environmental health and to prevent environmental pollution is citizens' duty.

To ensure that everyone continues their life in physical and mental health; In order to realize cooperation by increasing man and matter energy savings and efficiency, health institutions should be singled out, and the state plans and arranges service delivery. The state fulfills this duty by making use of the health and social institutions in the public and private sectors, by supervising them.

The state plans considers the characteristics of cities and environmental conditions.

It takes measures to meet the housing needs, and also supports mass housing enterprises.

Article 42.

Youth protection

The state ensures the protection of historical, cultural and natural assets and values, For this purpose, it takes supportive and encouraging measures.

Limitations on those assets and values that are privately owned, and For this reason, the aids and exemptions to be granted to the beneficiaries are regulated by law.

Article 43.

Union

Employees and employers, in order to protect and develop the economic and social rights of their members in their labor relations, without prior permission, have the right to establish unions and higher organizations or become a member freely, and to withdraw from membership freely. No one is a cannot be compelled to become a member of a union or to leave the membership.

The exercise of the right to form a union is based on the principles of the organic law.

Workers and employers mutually discuss their economic and social situation and their working conditions, have the right to conclude a collective bargaining agreement in order to regulate their conditions. How to make a collective bargaining agreement is regulated in organic law.

In case of disagreement during the conclusion of the collective bargaining agreement, the workers have the right to strike. The procedure and application of this right and the employer's application for lockout conditions, scope and exceptions are regulated by law. The right to strike and lockout cannot be used in violation of the rules of goodwill, to the detriment of the society and to the destruction of national wealth.

Civil servants and other public officials, collective bargaining they have the right.

Section III. Homework and Responsibility

Article I. Social Services

Article 44.

Study

It is the right and duty of every citizen to work and thus to contribute to humanity, the future of the country and the social order. The environment is also responsible in this regard.

The state takes measures to improve working life and protect the unemployed. Minors and women and those with physical and mental disabilities are specially protected in terms of working conditions.

Wages are compensation for labor; The person who will work has the right to ask for the wage he will receive in return for his labor. The state sets a minimum wage so that employees receive a fair wage appropriate to the work they do.

The employer ensures the social security of the employee to the extent of its responsibility.

The principles of practice regarding break, vacation, resignation, strike and collective dismissal for employers are regulated by organic Laws.

Article 45.

Public Service

Public service, even if it is paid, is the duty of the citizen and the environment is also responsible for this issue. This service has to be done by someone from among the citizens. The state takes measures for this and regulates the operation by law.

Every citizen has the right to enter public service. In recruitment, no discrimination other than the qualifications required by the job can be observed.

Article 46.

Military service

Military service is the right and duty of every citizen of the country. Terms and conditions of service are regulated by organic law.

The principles of service for women are regulated in organic law.

**Article II.
Social
Responsibilities**

Article 47.

Loyalty and Witnessing

The state expects loyalty and witnessing from its people under all circumstances. Loyalty is one's duty and witnessing is one's responsibility. Loyalty is loyalty to the state for and on behalf of the society by being faithful to the constitution.

A citizen cannot be deprived of citizenship unless he commits disloyalty. Judicial remedy cannot be closed against naturalization proceedings.

Article 48.

Legacy and Testament

The state has stated its express provision regarding the goods that the person has the right to own property according to the economic forecast that it has previously determined, or the goods that are considered the common property of the society, if any that the person uses temporarily; thus, it has regulated the laws necessary for inheritability as in organic laws.

Transferring the material and spiritual achievements of mankind to future generations bears a separate responsibility for the sanctity of the testator and

the survival of the state. Persons have to make a will and leave a legacy, if any, in accordance with this responsibility.

Disputes and disputes on these issues are settled by the courts.

Article 49.

Marriage

The state believes in love.

Marriage is a sacred union that creates and raises new and clean generations that will protect and develop all the past achievements of mankind.

Just as marriage is a right for man or woman, divorce is also a right according to the conditions in organic laws. The state has the right to divorce the persons it deems guilty according to the principles of organic laws.

A man cannot marry a man or a woman cannot marry a woman. The minimum age of marriage for men and women is 16. A man can have multiple marriages according to organic laws.

Having a child or adoption is a right protected by law.

The family is the foundation of society and is based on equality between spouses. Spouses are individuals who marry; They wish happiness for each other. A woman for a man and a man for a woman family is the first stage of education. The state is responsible for the peace and welfare of the family, especially the protection of the mother and children, and the family. takes the necessary measures to ensure that the planning is implemented and taught, establishes the organization

Marriage is officially documented.

Article 50.

Education and Learning

It is the duty of the individual to engage in educational and educational activities. The environment is also responsible for this.

In the light of the universal values of the Constitution, every citizen of the country has the right to be beneficial to all humanity with the principle of homeland first, and is responsible for contributing to scientific activities with a contemporary goal and to the extent of his situation and abilities.

Article 51.

Political Parties

Political parties are established without prior permission and carry out activities loyal to the principles of the Constitution. The state provides financial assistance to political parties.

Elections are held under the general management and supervision of the judicial organs.

Part II.
Management
Laws

Section I.
Legislative and Executive
Laws

Article I.
the Fundamentals

Article 52.
Representation

Any kind of trading activity carried out for the personal gain of a officers is strictly prohibited.

Members of the Assembly do not represent the region from which they are elected or those who elect them, but represent the whole nation with all their interests.

Article 53.
Induction

It is inducted in authorization.

All persons and departments, among whom the law of order and obedience has been established, are mutually responsible; All state elements, between which a labor law has been formed, have the rights required by the business in order to be tried after the expiration of this law for any reason.

Unlawful obedience and command are crimes. Every civil servant must serve the constitution faithfully.

Article II.
Execution Order
Terms

I. Basic legislative and executive powers

Article 54.
Grand National Assembly

The Grand National Assembly has the status of the Senate and is the highest assembly.

It is responsible for the legislative and executive. These powers are non-transferable. The judiciary has the right to save. It aims at permanent coalition regardless of the size of the constituent power.

The citizen has no direct relationship in the election of members. They are sent by the National Assemblies to represent them. It does not accept a non-citizen as a member.

Members of the Assembly may also be elected and appointed by the King by representatives of the people, if necessary, up to the number required for impeachment, and there is no age, gender, education or tenure restriction on the King in this regard. This election cannot be above the will of the parliament.

Assembly elects the Speaker of the Parliament, the Ministers and the Prime Minister himself. The Speaker of the House only chairs the session. The Prime Minister and Ministers are responsible for the executive.

Executive leaders in the assembly are known and referred to as the Council of Elders. The Ministers of the Council of Elders are responsible for establishing or developing undersecretariats; appointments and the form and principles of the organization are as in organic laws. The undersecretaries they set up or the undersecretaries they appoint are binding with the approval of the King.

The Grand National Assembly has the authority to use the army.

Article 55.

Ministries

The ministries are responsible for the executive and the legislature. Its leader is the minister of state. It represents the government. There is only the following ministries:

- Prime Ministry
- Ministry of Internal Affairs
- Ministry of Foreign Affairs
- Ministry of Health
- Ministry of Justice
- Ministry of Defense
- Ministry of Finance
- Ministry of Education

Article 56.

Undersecretariat

The executive affairs of the ministries are carried out through the Undersecretariats.

The government does not open or close new ministries. Instead, it establishes or closes undersecretariats attached to the main ministries.

Article 57.

Council of Elders

The notables of the Grand National Assembly are the Council of Elders. It is the highest body representing the government.

The Council of Elders consists of the Prime Minister, Ministers responsible for Internal and Foreign Affairs, Defense, Education, Justice, Health and Economy, and the civil administrator from the dynasty with the title of Melik, representing the governors. These are the most authoritative people after the King and have no superiority over each other. Melik is responsible for the execution, representing the central administration.

The members of the delegation constitute the National Security Council; as such, it becomes an advisory board. Making decisions regarding the determination and implementation of the national security policy; He is responsible for notifying the King of his views on the institutional and inter-institutional activities that should be carried out in this direction.

The committee has administrative sanction powers as a member or a board. Members of the delegation, individually or as a council, cannot act above the will of the Grand National Assembly.

The Minister of Defense becomes minister by appointment of the Council of the Army and the Minister of Justice by the appointment of the Council of the Judiciary and with the approval of the King. There is no requirement for the highest rank or experience. Upon the acceptance of their resignation following the investigation initiated due to their activities during their ministry, if there is no legal objection, they may receive assignments as a requirement of the training they have received.

A possible dispute regarding the appointment and approval of the Minister of Defense and Justice requires a no-confidence vote, and accordingly, the majority of the votes of the Grand National Assembly are binding.

Article 58.

King

The king is the head of the executive and army on behalf of the people. This authority is non-transferable.

The king cannot amend the constitution alone, cannot decide on war,

and cannot act above the will of the parliament. The Assembly can reject its decision only once.

The king can change only when a majority vote is achieved in the popular vote. He has the right to remain in the lead indefinitely.

Keeping state secrets is a reason for the King to take action.

Granting or deprivation of citizenship, exile and death sentences, and pardon of imprisonment are binding only by the King's vote, and the King alone cannot transfer these rights.

Article 59.

Dynasty

The king is from the dynasty and is male. If all of his mental, spiritual and sexual conditions are healthy, he can be elected king at any age.

A woman cannot be elected as king, even by referendum. If there is no son, the people choose a king from other family members.

Melik is elected only from the dynasty.

Article 60.

Advisory Council

It is the King's Privy Council. He assists the King in overseeing the government and administering the state, and gives opinions only.

The King chooses his members as he pleases. There is no age or gender restriction on the King in this regard.

As a member or a council, the Assembly has administrative sanction powers. Members of the Assembly, individually or as a council, cannot act above the will of the Grand National Assembly or the members of the Assembly.

The Consultative Council does not have the authority to use the army.

II. Administration

A. Sub-Assemblies

Article 61.

State Assemblies

The State Legislature is made up of states only and exists in every state. It is the Board of Control. It consists of permanent members whose members are appointed for the assembly and appointed in relation to their duties. The leader is titled Beylerbeyi; He has the title of Civil Administrative Officer.

The public has no direct influence on the election of Beylerbeyi. Assignment is key.

The state legislature cannot use the military.

Article 62.

National Assembly

The National Assembly is established exclusively for provinces and there is only one in each province. Its members are MPs. The leader is titled Bey; He has the title of Civil Administrative Officer. Bey is directly elected by the people.

Mission; It is the administration of provinces, districts and sub-districts in every respect.

Provincial Health Director, Provincial Chief Public Prosecutor, Provincial Police Chief, Provincial Treasurer and Provincial Garrison Commander are permanent members; They are not elected by citizens or the National Assembly.

The National Assembly cannot use the army.

B. Institutions

Article 63.

Royal Academy

The Royal Academy is the largest and most respected binding science institution.

The Royal Higher Education Council is the only binding scientific and administrative body acting on behalf of the public for the purpose of education and training. Higher education institutions affiliated to the Armed Forces and the Security Organization, subject to the provisions of special laws.

Board members are elected from the Academy.

Article 64.

Central Bank

The Central Bank manages the country's monetary policies. It acts autonomously, away from direct political pressures, in making and implementing monetary policy decisions. Orders and instructions cannot be given.

Article 65.

Social Security Institution

The Social Security Institution is obliged to provide assurance regarding the basic needs and social relations of the citizen on behalf of the public and on behalf of the state, regardless of their status or income; In line with this purpose, the state takes the necessary measures and regulates the implementation with organic law.

Article 66.

Standards Institution

It is established in order to prepare and have all kinds of standards prepared, to examine the standards prepared within and outside, and to publish accepted standards.

C. Organizations

Article 67.

National Intelligence Agency

National Intelligence Agency; It is an organization that is tasked with collecting information about current or potential threats to the independence and integrity of the country, the constitutional order, security and all other elements, from inside and outside, to take precautions to the extent of its authority and to warn the relevant authorities if necessary.

It acts under the Prime Ministry and its president gains the title of under-secretary. **Article 68.**

Law Enforcement

The Police Department is the state organization responsible for the internal security of the state. The officers have the title of Police.

Its duty is to maintain general security and internal order in accordance with the law and procedure, together with the citizen; To perform the duties predetermined for them by the laws about a crime that has been committed.

The police force is subject to order as a law enforcement force. It operates under the Ministry of Internal Affairs.

Article 69.

Organization of Ombudsmen

Central administration, local administrations, public corporations; it ensures that all institutions and organizations providing public services, as well as their personalities, act in accordance with the constitution.

Anyone who thinks that a right has been violated for himself or for a citizen can apply to the Ombudsman Organization in accordance with the principles set forth in the organic law.

Since it has to be autonomous and impartial by its job description, it acts under the Grand National Assembly on behalf of the people. Its President is the Ombudsman.

The Ombudsman Organization, how it can get help from third parties during the exercise of its powers, what powers it will use and to what extent, and the state budget attached to them are regulated by organic law.

The Chief Ombudsman is elected by the Grand National Assembly.

III. Officers

Article 70.

General principles

The state must provide assistance to the administrator. There cannot be a manager without an assistant. Citizens are not responsible for inadequate measures.

The administration imposes a penal action that is not restrictive of freedom. Unless the right of defense is granted to civil servants and other public officials, members of professional organizations in the nature of public institutions and their superior organizations, disciplinary punishment cannot be imposed. Administrative penalties cannot be excluded from judicial review. Provisions regarding members of the Armed Forces, judges and prosecutors are reserved.

Compensation lawsuits caused by faults committed by civil servants and other public officials while exercising their authority, can only be brought against the administration and in accordance with the form and conditions indicated by the law.

Punishment for the crimes they allegedly committed against civil servants and other public officials opening a prosecution depends on the permission of the administrative authority indicated by the law, except for the exceptions determined by the law.

Qualifications, appointments, duties and powers, rights and obligations, salaries and allowances and other personnel matters of civil servants and other public officials are regulated by law. However, the provisions of collective agreements regarding financial and social rights are reserved.

The methods and principles of training senior managers are regulated specifically by law.

Those who enter the public service must declare their property and that these declarations repetition times are regulated by law. Those who serve in the legislative and executive organs, cannot be excluded.

Article III. Applications

I. Political Practices

Article 71.

History, cultural and natural assets

The state ensures the protection of historical, cultural and natural assets and values, For this purpose, it takes supportive and encouraging measures.

Limitations on those assets and values that are privately owned, and For this reason, the aids and exemptions to be granted to the beneficiaries are regulated by law.

Article 72.

Language

Spoken language is the officially declared language. The only language that must be learned is the official language.

The official language must be protected and developed by the state; The state takes the necessary measures for this. Other languages that the public is free to speak are also subject to this protection.

II. Forensic Applications

Article 73.

Death Penalty

The state imposes the death penalty in the case of judicial or self-defense.

III. Administrative Applications

Article 74.

State of Emergency

State of emergency, martial law, mobilization, laws of war and war, compulsory conditions of war and their application forms and principles are determined by organic laws. The state is always ready for any adverse situation.

There is no person or institution that cannot be prosecuted, and the state suspends the constitutional rights of all individuals and institutions when necessary, in accordance with the principles of the constitution.

Article 75.

Nationalization and Privatization

State and public legal entities; In cases where the public interest requires, all or part of the immovable property in private property, It is authorized to expropriate and establish administrative servitudes on them in accordance with the principles and procedures indicated. There is a payment requirement real monetary compensation in advance. Private enterprises with a public service nature can be nationalized when the public interest is necessary. Nationalization is done over real monetary equivalent. The manner in which the fair value was calculated, and procedures are regulated by law.

State, state-owned enterprises and other public; principles and procedures regarding the privatization of enterprises and assets owned by the legal entities indicated by law.

IV. Social and Economic Practices

Article 76.

Planning and Supervision

There is a planning and inspection organization in order to contribute to the economic, social and cultural development of the state.

Its duty is to make plans for the entire existence of the state, to present them to the government and to supervise it. It is regulated by organic law.

It is subordinate to the Grand National Assembly.

Article 77.

Cooperatives

The state, taking into account the benefits of the national economy, shall first and foremost ensure that production measures to ensure the development of cooperatives aiming to increase and protect consumers He takes it.

Article 78.

Exploration and exploitation of natural wealth and resources

Natural wealth and resources are under the rule and disposal of the State. These The right to explore and operate belongs to the State. The state may exercise this right for a certain period of time, real and may be transferred to legal entities. What natural wealth and resource exploration and operation is the State's real and to be done jointly with legal persons or directly by real and legal persons, subject to the express permission of the law, it depends. In this case, the conditions that natural and legal persons must comply with and the surveillance to be carried out by the State, audit procedures and principles and sanctions are indicated in the law.

Article 79.

Consumer protection

The state takes protective and enlightening measures for consumers and encourages consumers to protect themselves.

V. Military Applications

Article 80.

Army

The state carries out the armed defense of the country with the regular and permanent Armed Forces army.

Article 81.

Disarmament

The government is restrained in its defense spending. It supports international disarmament as well as taking defensive measures.

It accepts international conventions as enlightening, stimulating and binding.

Article 82.

Weapons of Mass Destruction

State; prohibits the development, production, stockpiling and use of nuclear, chemical and biological weapons.

Nuclear power with the effect of mass destruction cannot be used for defensive purposes.

VI. Educational Applications

Article 83.

Compulsory Education

Compulsory education is at primary level for boys and girls. Primary education is the first stage of education. The age of starting education and the duration of education are as in the organic law.

Article 84.

Educational Institutions

Post-primary education begins with high school; High schools are the secondary level of education.

Education at the higher education level is given through the College and the university.

Training periods are the same as in the organic law.

VII. Scientific Applications

Article 85.

Protection of science

Its universal and conceptual value is essential in the making of science.

Under no circumstances can the scientific process and scientist be hindered. The state protects and supports scientific activities and scientists.

A scientist cannot be forced to do work in war or peace. Their laws arising from their international identity or representation are respected.

Article 86.

Nuclear Plan

The state is obliged to take the necessary measures with the condition of achieving nuclear competence and using it in accordance with its purpose.

The development, deployment and use of nuclear power cannot be excluded from the control of the Grand National Assembly.

Part II.
Judgment
Laws

Article I.
the Fundamentals

Article 87.

Principled judgment

The principles that are essential for the trial are as follows:

- No provision can be made that has no place in the law.
- All are equal before the law; the righteous is superior,
- There must be proportionality between the crime and its punishment.
- The principle of innocence in trial cannot be ignored.
- No one can be tried and convicted on behalf of another.
- Every citizen is considered to know the law; Everyone has to voluntarily admit their guilt or admit their mistake.
- Laws cannot be enforced retrospectively.
- The widespread use of crime does not justify it.
- Until proven guilty in a court of law, no one can be considered guilty.
- No one is allowed to make a statement incriminating himself or his relatives shown in the law or cannot be compelled to show evidence in this way.
- Findings obtained illegally, as evidence unacceptable.

These principles and application principles do not change according to time and do not change according to the person.

Article 88.

Jurisdiction

The judiciary is impartial, its symbol is the scales, its command is conscience and its conscience is factual.

Judging is done through the stage of argument and judgment; its profession is that of prosecutor and judge.

Judgment is made by prosecutors and judges in the name of the people through jurisprudence and by adhering to the conceptual spirit of the constitution. The judgment is the judge's.

Members of the judiciary are prosecutors, judges and lawyers. Members of the judiciary are judged; the rule of law is paramount.

Translated with www.DeepL.com/Translator (free version)

Article II. Provisions

I. General order of the courts

Article 89.

Courts

Courts are autonomous and impartial.

No organ, authority, or person can give orders and instructions to judges; cannot send circulars; cannot make recommendations or suggestions. No questions may be asked, debated or statements made regarding the exercise of jurisdiction in the Legislative Assembly on a pending case.

Courts may impose the death penalty for people who have lost their right to live in accordance with the principles of the law. However, giving a life sentence is among the powers, duties and responsibilities of the courts. Situations where such heavy penalties conflict with human rights are determined by law.

No decision is binding without justification.

Every citizen has the right to a fair trial through the courts at no cost. Everyone is entitled to before the judicial authorities by making use of legitimate means and means. The plaintiff or the defendant has the right to claim and defense and to a fair trial.

Court hearings are open to everyone. It can only be decided to make it completely closed only in cases where public morality or public safety absolutely necessitates it.

Article 90.

Minority Tribunal

People of different religions have their own independent courts, despite possible conflicts between the laws.

Trial of people of different religions; As long as it is not contrary to human rights, their own religion or the constitution, including the death decision, these courts are made and the principles of application are the same as in organic laws.

Ethnic minorities cannot establish courts.

II. Courthouse

Article 91.

Constitutional Court

The Constitutional Court is the highest court and is the last resort for individuals and institutions of any status.

The Constitutional Court is also considered the judicial power of the Grand National Assembly due to its identity as the Council of the Judiciary and its competence in its work on behalf of the people. It accepts the vote of all official members of the judiciary and their representatives in the capacity of its own Judicial Council and on the basis of legal disputes against the Grand National Assembly in the amendment and implementation of the Constitution.

Constitutional Court; constitution, parliamentary decrees and conformity of organic laws to the constitution in terms of form and substance audits and decides on individual applications. While annulling a constitutional amendment, a law or a decree having the force of law, it cannot act as a legislator in a way that will lead to a new application.

The Supreme Court is the identity of the Constitutional Court, where it judges the legislative and executive persons on behalf of the people.

Article 92.

The Court of Cassation

The Court of Cassation is the final examination authority of the decisions and judgments given by the courts of law that the law does not leave to another judicial jurisdiction. It also considers certain cases specified by law as a court of first and last instance.

It represents the judiciary, the supreme court.

III. Executive Courts

Article 93.

State Council

The Council of State is the final examination authority of the decisions and judgments given by the administrative courts that the law does not leave to another administrative jurisdiction. It also considers certain cases specified by law as a court of first and last instance.

It represents the executive, the supreme court.

Article 94.

The Court of Accounts

The Court of Accounts deals with public administrations within the scope of the central government budget and social all income, expenses and property of security institutions on behalf of the Grand National Assembly. to control the accounts and transactions of those responsible and to make final decisions and to It is responsible for examining, supervising and adjudicating.

It represents the executive, the supreme court.

IV. Military Courts

Article 95.

Military judgment

Military justice is carried out by military courts and disciplinary courts. These courts; military persons It is in charge of hearing the military crimes committed by the military and the crimes committed by them against military personnel or in connection with their military service and duties. Cases related to crimes against the security of the state, the constitutional order and the functioning of this order are always heard in the courts of justice.

Apart from the war, non-military people can not be tried in military courts.

For which crimes and which persons military courts are authorized in case of war; organizations and when necessary, the appointment of judicial judges and prosecutors in these courts shall be regulated by law.

The establishment and functioning of military judicial organs, the personnel affairs of military judges, the relations of military judges performing military prosecutor's duties with the commander in charge are regulated by law in accordance with the principles of the independence of the courts and the guarantee of judgeship.

Article 96.

Military Administrative Court

Even if the Supreme Military Administrative Court is established by non-military authorities, it is the first and last instance court that conducts judicial review of disputes arising from administrative acts and actions related to military service. However, in disputes arising from military obligation, the condition of being a military person is not sought.

It represents the executive, the supreme court.

Article 97.

Military Supreme Court

The Military Court of Cassation is the final review authority of the decisions and judgments rendered by the military courts. In addition, it deals with certain cases of military persons indicated by law as a court of first and last instance.

It represents the judiciary, the supreme court.

V. Court of Appeals

Article 98.

Administrative and judicial dispute

The Court of Disputes is authorized to definitively resolve conflicts of duty and provision between judicial and administrative jurisdictions.

In disputes between other courts and the Constitutional Court, the Constitution The decision of the court is taken as the basis.

It represents the judiciary, the supreme court.

Section III.

Army

Laws

Article I.

the Fundamentals

Article 99.

Army's homework

The main purpose of the army is to carry out the armed defense of the country. It can act to protect the weak against the strong or to prevent injustices in the international arena in order to maintain world peace. It cannot be used for other purposes.

Article 100.

Fundamentals of Operation

An order of operation is not binding without a duly, clear and reasoned declaration of war by the legal authorities.

The Principle of Last Resort is essential in any military operation; The condition of action arises when responsibilities in line with mutual interests are not ignored, universal humanitarian goals and methods are not met, and all other legal remedies are blocked.

Even under attack, except in cases of compulsory warfare, a collective war cannot be waged without the order of the King. The army is at the disposal of the nation.

Internal rebellions cannot be counted as wars; the state, with its natural and traditional order, must have taken precautionary measures against the rebellions.

During war or rebellion, the civilian population cannot be taken to the streets unconditionally, armed or unarmed. The King or ruler who gives orders to the people collectively is tried with high treason and has no right to live.

Article II.

Provisions

Article 101.

Army order

The army is the regular and standing army in war and peace. The Commander-in-Chief is the King by proxy; Army commanders lead the army.

Article 102.

Defense order

Defense is done by the armed forces on behalf of the people.

Article 103.

Army Assembly

The army takes the parliamentary order with the identity that it represents the people. In this respect, it is considered as one of the basic elements of the executive.

Army Assembly; It consists of the Chief of the General Staff, Force Commanders and other Armed Forces Members elected in accordance with constitutional procedures and principles. The Army Assembly is chaired by the Chief of the General Staff and is not subordinate to the Minister of Defense in the administration of the army.

Göktuğ takes decisions within the scope of his responsibility in cases of emergency.

Article 104.

Law of War

Unjustified military activity cannot be carried out under this pretext, even during the war.

In war, bondage is essential. The soldier is not treated as a criminal, but as a prisoner of war, because he does not act individually, but acts under his authority and against his will. The elderly, women and children are not touched; It cannot be taken prisoner and used for service purposes.

The use of weapons and violence commensurate with the justification of the war is essential. Loot, plunder and rape are prohibited; the perpetrator is executed.

Agreements of Non-Aggression in directing war are considered binding in war.

International agreements are considered binding as well as enlightening and warning status for the state on the law of war.

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